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ABSTRACT

Research and innovation in particle accelerator science and technology is key to the progress of strategic scientific fields where Europe holds a leadership position. Moreover, accelerators are increasingly being used in health care and industry, where the availability of new accelerator technologies can improve our life quality and generate economic growth. After several decades of European prominence, in the present critical moment for the evolution of particle accelerators the increasing pressure from Asia and new far-sighted US initiatives are putting at risk the European role in this crucial scientific and technological field. After giving an overview of its main challenges and of the present instruments to coordinate and support particle accelerator research and innovation in Europe, this report presents some conclusions from the Working Groups active within the ARIES project on how to enhance industry involvement, showing as a successful example the preparation of the new I.FAST project.

Finally, the report presents some guidelines and a roadmap identified within ARIES towards creating a sustainable ecosystem for particle accelerator research and innovation in Europe, capable of preserving the European leading position in accelerator-based scientific fields and its related advantages for high-technology European industry and for the whole European society.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

Research and innovation in particle accelerator science and technology is key to the progress of strategic scientific fields where Europe holds a leadership position. Moreover, accelerators are increasingly being used in health care and industry, where the availability of new accelerator technologies leads to new products improving our quality of life and generating economic growth. After decades of steady progress with a clear European prominence, particle accelerators are now facing a critical stage in their evolution. While more performant and sustainable accelerator technologies are needed to support new initiatives in basic and applied science, the combination of an increasing pressure from Asia and new far-sighted US initiatives are putting at risk the European position in this strategic scientific and technological field.

After giving an overview of the present structures and instruments to coordinate and support particle accelerator research and innovation in Europe and summarising the main challenges of this quite unique research field, this report presents some conclusions from the Working Groups active within the ARIES project on how to enhance industry involvement showing as a successful example the preparation of the new I.FAST project.

Finally, the report presents some guidelines and a roadmap identified within ARIES towards creating a sustainable ecosystem for particle accelerator research and innovation in Europe, capable of preserving the European leading position in accelerator-based scientific fields and its related advantages for high-technology European industry and for the whole European society.

1. The impact of particle accelerators on European Science, Technology, and Industry

Particle accelerators are a strategic asset of modern science and technology. They are our unique tool to access the atomic and subatomic dimensions, directly interacting with the atomic nuclei and their components, and to generate intense secondary beams of various particles. Conceived as scientific instruments to discover fundamental laws and structures of physics, they have now extended their range of application to become powerful sources of photons or neutrons to visualise atomic and molecular structures with impact on research fields as varied as life science, condensed matter, energy research, engineering materials and geosciences, environmental science, material science, cultural heritage. In parallel, multiple accelerator applications in medicine, industrial production, environmental protection, energy, and security have been seized by the industrial sector generating a multi-billion accelerator market that improves our quality of life and our industrial products, creating employment and economic growth.

The strong impact of particle accelerators on science is well demonstrated by the large amount of Nobel prizes related to accelerator technology. In Physics, 25 out of the last 74 Nobel prizes were achieved using particle accelerators [1]. X-Rays sources, mostly provided by particle accelerators, were used in research that was awarded with 20 Nobel Prizes in Chemistry, Physics and Medicine [2]. Although the most visible, accelerators operating for science are only a small fraction, about 5%,

of the more than 40'000 particle accelerators presently in operation worldwide. The large majority of accelerators is used in everyday industrial and medical practice, where the most notable fields of application are ion implantation in semiconductors (34% of all accelerators), and cancer therapy (33%).

The impact of particle accelerators on European science can be easily demonstrated by the size of the user communities making use of accelerators for their research. Particle physics is the best-known discipline relying on particle accelerators, represented at European level by the 12'500 users of CERN [3], the European Organization for Nuclear Research, the largest and most advanced particle physics laboratory worldwide. Its users represent 110 nationalities, coming from institutes based in more than 70 countries, with a strong representation from the US and Asia.

Beyond particle physics, a rapidly growing community of accelerator users is linked to “photon science”, exploiting intense X-ray beams produced by accelerator-based synchrotron light or free electron laser facilities. In Europe are based more than 20 light sources, many of them already upgraded or being upgraded with the latest accelerator technologies, representing about 40% of the more than 50 light sources in the world, operational or under construction [4]. They serve a multi-disciplinary user community estimated at about 30'000 researchers [5].

In a complementary way to photons, accelerator-produced neutrons are also used as a probe for condensed matter studies by a growing community of more than 5'000 researchers, presently in full transition from exploiting reactor-based neutron sources to accelerator-based source of new generation as the European Spallation Source in Lund, Sweden [6].

Another historical and well-established user community of accelerators is related to research in nuclear physics. An estimate of its extent is more complex than for other communities, but already adding the number of users at the major European nuclear physics facilities (GSI, GANIL, INFN National Laboratories) we arrive to more than 3'000 users.

The result of this simple analysis is that **the European particle accelerator infrastructure supports more than 50'000 users in a wide range of scientific domains.**

Beyond their role in science, small particle accelerators for use in medicine and industry are becoming commercial products, supporting a global annual market estimated in 2018 to ~US\$5.0 billion/year with a >5% annual growth [7]. A precise estimate of the European fraction of this market is not available, but the fact that about 20% of worldwide accelerator vendors are based in Europe leads to estimating the European particle accelerator market at about 1 billion euros per year.

Together with their impact on the economy, the domain of accelerators for medicine brings another fundamental impact, on the health and well-being of cancer patients treated every year with accelerators. As reported by the official UK cancer treatment statistics, 27% of patients diagnosed with cancer (all cancers combined) in England during 2013-2014 had as part of their primary cancer treatment curative or palliative radiotherapy, delivered by X-rays produced with a particle accelerator [8]. In absolute numbers, this corresponds to almost 100'000 radiotherapy patients per year in the UK. Access to radiation therapy in most European countries is similar to that in UK, leading to an

estimate of more than half million of patients per year profiting of accelerator-based radiation therapy in Europe.

More accurate in dose delivery than X-rays, beams of protons or heavier ions directly produced by large particle accelerators have been used to deliver advanced cancer therapy to more than 60'000 European patients since the introduction of this treatment modality at the end of the 90's. [9]. Cancer therapy with protons is rapidly expanding, while new accelerator technologies are being developed to extend the reach of therapy with heavier ions. Presently, more than 7'000 patients per year are treated with proton or ion beams in Europe, at 34 facilities [9].

Altogether, the European accelerator landscape is extremely diversified and largely successful. While the 2013 Nobel Prize to Englert and Higgs for the discovery of the Higgs boson at the CERN accelerators has demonstrated the European prominence in particle physics, this success represents only the most visible part of the European leading position in terms of number of accelerator-based facilities and scientific output. A recent US study acknowledges that more than 40% of the >200 worldwide accelerator-based scientific facilities are based in Europe [10].

2. Particle Accelerator Research and Innovation in Europe

2.1 THE NEED FOR RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

Notwithstanding their wide usage and success, particle accelerators are at a critical moment in their evolution. Almost 10 years after the discovery of the Higgs boson, expectations are high for more physics discoveries answering basic questions like extent and origin of dark matter or matter-antimatter asymmetry, but the requirements in terms of size, cost and electrical power of future high-energy accelerator projects make their funding and implementation increasingly difficult. New accelerator technologies are critically needed, to continue in a sustainable way our exploration of the physics world, contributing at the same time to extending the reach and the accuracy of our accelerator-based photon and neutron sources. Moreover, new designs and technologies would pave the way to more compact, less expensive and more performant accelerators for medicine and industry, opening new markets and extending the field of accelerator applications. Recently emphasized by the 2020 update of the European Strategy for Particle Physics [11], the need for a vigorous R&D effort on particle accelerators will allow retaining the European leading position in particle physics and more in general in the cutting-edge scientific domains exploiting particle accelerators, strengthening at the same time the European presence in high-technology markets.

To achieve valuable results and to sustain the competition with US and China, a renovated effort on particle accelerator research and innovation (R&I) is drastically needed, based on the combined effort of the main European actors in accelerator R&I and of the European Commission.

Before defining the requirements to make accelerator R&I effective and sustainable, an overview of its specific challenges and an analysis of the present instruments for collaborative accelerator R&I will be presented.

2.2 CHALLENGES OF PARTICLE ACCELERATOR R&I

Research and Innovation for particle accelerators in Europe present some specific challenges, identified within the ARIES working groups as:

- **Long development times.** Key accelerator components, like new superconducting magnets, require development times of 10 or more years, followed by even longer design, construction and implementation times. An example in this respect are the superconducting magnets for the Large Hadron Collider, which required ten years to go from a conceptual design stage in 1984 to the end of prototyping in 1994. The following design, construction, and commissioning phase took more than another decade, until first beam acceleration in 2008. Much longer development times are needed to define new accelerator designs. The CLIC (Compact Linear Collider) Study at CERN started in 1985, to produce a first Conceptual Design Report in 2012, complemented by some updates between 2016 and 2018 [12]. The time scale is not much different for commercial accelerators. Interesting examples reported in [7] are ion implanters, that required 22 years between first proposal and commercialisation, medical electron linacs that came to market in a record 13 years, and proton beam therapy with as much as 38 years between first proposal and first operational accelerator.
- **High integrated development costs.** Even at a small level of funding per year, the integrated development costs of new accelerator designs and components can be extremely high. Development and prototyping of new accelerator technologies usually reaches the M€ level, while new accelerator concepts can require investments at the level of several hundred M€'s. For example, the CLIC study has been supported for many years at CERN at a level of 2% of the CERN budget, corresponding to a total investment higher than 500 M€.
- **Fragmentation of the R&D actors.** The European landscape of institutions active in particle accelerator R&I is divided horizontally, among different user communities exploiting accelerators each with its own support network, and vertically among a large number of research institutions of different kinds: operators of Research Infrastructures, national and international research centres, universities, and industry. Over the last 18 years, more than 100 institutions in 21 countries have in different ways participated in collaborative accelerator R&D projects supported by the European Commission. This fragmentation reflects the complex structure of the European Research Area but also the interest that particle accelerator R&D represents for smaller research entities and universities, as an ideal training area for students merging theoretical and practical competences.
- **High risk.** Particle accelerator R&D remains a high-risk endeavour, exploring new technological territories where success at first try is never guaranteed. Additional time and funding are the typical risk mitigations for accelerator R&D programmes, making their budgeting and scheduling particularly challenging.

2.3 EUROPEAN SUPPORT TO PARTICLE ACCELERATOR R&I

To address these challenges, over the past 18 years a total of 22 coordinated Accelerator R&D projects have been supported within the different Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Commission, with a total cost of 333 M€ and an EC contribution of 123 M€ corresponding to an average of 6.8 M€/year. They have contributed to enhancing collaboration and integration of the Accelerator Research area, via the development of common instruments and methodologies for the accelerator community, and have fostered the development and construction of several accelerator facilities like Linac4 at CERN, ELBE, FLASH, EU-XFEL, ESS, HL-LHC, FAIR, etc. The instruments used so far are a combination of Integrating Activities, Design Studies, Preparatory Phase Projects, plus the recent Innovation Pilot.

The preparation and submission of the projects have been successfully coordinated by two bodies that in subsequent times have been formed within the particle accelerator community:

- **ESGARD**, the European Strategy Group on Accelerator Research and Development, established in 2002 by the directors of seven primary accelerator research institutions (CCLRC, CERN, DAPNIA/CEA, DESY, LNF-INFN, Orsay/IN2P3, and PSI) in consultation with ECFA (European Committee on Future Accelerators).
- **TIARA**, the Test Infrastructure and Accelerator Research Area, which was initiated as a FP7 Preparatory Phase project with the goal of integrating national and international accelerator R&D infrastructures into a single distributed European accelerator R&D facility [13]. This objective includes the implementation of organisational structures going beyond ESGARD, to enable the integration of existing individual infrastructures, their efficient operation and upgrades, and the construction of new infrastructures. The TIARA preparatory phase project covered the period 2010-2013 and resulted in the creation of a permanent TIARA Collaboration Council that in 2015 replaced ESGARD. The TIARA Collaboration is structured as a Consortium of European Research Institutions operating significant R&D Infrastructures in the European Particle Accelerator Research Area, with the goal of creating a dedicated structure to exchange expertise and to facilitate and support the setting-up of joint R&D programmes and education and training in the field of Accelerator Science and Technology in Europe [14]. The Collaboration is based on a Memorandum of Understanding among 11 partners signed in April 2015, recently (2020) joined by the Baltic Group, an association of research institutions in the Baltics. The partners are expected to contribute to the activities of TIARA with an in-kind or cash contribution.

In almost 20 years of activity, ESGARD and TIARA have contributed to the creation of an ecosystem of collaboration and exchange within the wider particle accelerator community, engaging universities and industry on top of the traditional actors of accelerator R&I into common projects to advance particle accelerator science and technology. Figure 1 presents the evolution of number and overall EC contribution of the accelerator-related EU projects coordinated by ESGARD/TIARA in the period 2004 – 2020, with a projection until 2025 including already approved projects. All ESGARD/TIARA projects are co-funded, with the partners engaging internal resources usually at the level of 50% of total project cost.

Figure 1: Yearly number and EC contribution of ESGARD/TIARA projects in 2004/2025

The backbone of the ESGARD/TIARA projects is made of 4 subsequent Integrating Activity projects, followed recently by an Innovation Pilot approved in the last call of the Horizon 2020 Programme. The projects with their timeline and funding are presented in Fig. 2. This sequence of five projects has provided EC support to research and innovation in the accelerator community at an average level of 2.5 M€ per year. Including the internal resources from the partners, they have mobilised resources for about 5 M€ per year.

Figure 2: Particle Accelerator Integrating Activities and Innovation Pilot, 2004-2025

The collaborative Integrating Activities and Innovation Pilot are not intended to support specific projects or individual development programmes of the partners. Their mission instead is to connect European initiatives transversally and to identify and promote common directions and strategies for the long-term development of accelerator technologies covering different types of accelerators and benefitting different user communities (Figure 3). The goal of these projects is to create and structure a European Accelerator Research Area federating partners from different accelerator communities, creating connections at three different levels:

- across communities, linking accelerators for particle physics, nuclear physics, photon and neutron science, medical and industrial applications.
- across different innovation players, linking Research Infrastructure operators with national and international research organisations, universities, and industry.
- across European countries and regions, linking traditional actors of accelerator development in the more scientifically advanced regions of Europe with new players from the dynamic European periphery.

Figure 3: Accelerator Science and Technology serving different applications and user communities.

Although very successful, this supporting scheme presents some problems and limitations:

- The projects have a duration (4 years) much shorter than the development times of new accelerator technologies. The consequence is that longer developments must be split into stages making long-term planning virtually impossible. An additional element of risk comes from the fact that initiatives to support particle accelerators are in competition with all other scientific communities, requiring a considerable effort to regularly prepare outstanding proposals capable of succeeding in a very competitive environment, with no guarantee of success and of funding.
- The selection of R&D topics to be included in the projects is based on criteria and structures defined ad-hoc internally to the accelerator community and re-defined for each project. Although the community is striving to incorporate the needs of the different accelerator user communities and the requirements from the European Commission, the lack of formalised connections with users and with industry as well as the limited interaction with the European Commission permitted during project preparation may limit the impact of particle accelerator projects.

3. Accelerator R&I programmes in the US and Asia

Conscious of the increasing important of particle accelerators in scientific research conducted in the United States (US) and of the strong worldwide competition in accelerator-based science facilities, the US Department of Energy (DOE) has established in April 2020 the Office of Accelerator R&D and Production (ARDAP). Its mission is to coordinate and boost accelerator R&D and production investments aimed at ensuring that future U.S. accelerator-based physical science R&D priorities will be met. By facilitating the coordination of R&D investments and by directly investing in selected cross-cutting areas in accelerator science and technology (AS&T), its ambitious objectives are to “ensure a robust pipeline of next-generation AS&T to support physical sciences research while providing technology advances and industrial strength that position the U.S. to lead the world for decades to come” [10]. One of the key arguments for this renovated US interest in accelerator research is that Asia, and China in particular, are taking an increasingly visible role in accelerator research, at the expenses of the US, and in a minor extent of Europe. Figure 4 from [10] shows that while in 2011 one out of four papers on accelerator science and technology downloaded from Web of Science was from the U.S, this number in 2020 has shrunk to less than one in eight. The number of papers from Europe was about 35% in 2011, went up to 40-45% in 2012-13 to go down again to 30-35% in the period 2018-20.

Figure 4: Papers on accelerator science and technology downloaded from Web of Science by geographical region, 2011-2020.

The first action of the new Office has been launching an Accelerator Science & Technology Initiative (ASTI) as a multi-million initiative to support accelerator R&D in Fiscal Year 2022 and beyond, with the goal of creating a robust ecosystem to support accelerator R&D in the US. In Financial Year 2021, the DOE’s Strategic Accelerator Technology Initiative (SATI) has distributed at total of 13.5 M\$ divided among accelerators for Basic Energy, High Energy Physics, and Nuclear Physics [10].

In parallel, the pattern of high funding for science and in particular for accelerator science is continuing in China. Plans for a 100-km collider for particle physics are continuing, while new

facilities for synchrotron light and neutron science are starting operation. Several laboratories and universities are involved in accelerator R&I, with a strong governmental support.

Japan is now planning a strong boost in its spending for accelerators, aim at construction in Japan of the International Linear Collider, a multi-billion international project expected to take leadership in particle physics research and to have a wide economical impact on Japanese industry. In parallel, since many years Japan is a leader in collaborative projects between accelerator laboratories and industry, which have contributed to giving Japanese industry a strong competitive advantage in fields like particle therapy of cancer.

4. Involving European Industry in Accelerator R&I

Innovative European companies, in particular SME's, are a key asset of the European Research Area with a strong potential for contributing to accelerator R&I. To explore opportunities for collaboration with industry in accelerator research and innovation, a joint Working Group was established within ARIES, involving the TIARA Collaboration, the parallel AMICI (Accelerator and Magnet Infrastructure for Cooperation and Innovation) EU Project, and representatives of industries already involved in co-innovation projects on accelerators. The goal of the Working Group was to analyse future perspectives for joint projects within the accelerator community and further ways to involve industry. To discuss this subject within a larger community and to involve the Research Infrastructure Unit of the EC Research Directorate, the Working Group organised a Workshop that took place in Brussels on 6 – 7 February 2018, under the title “Enhancing co-innovation with industry in the Particle Accelerator Community” [15].

The objectives of the Workshop were: a) to foster discussion on most effective ways to develop co-innovation with industry in Europe; b) to identify sustainable structures, possible funding schemes and financing mechanisms; c) to contribute to the definition of new EC instruments to boost co-innovation; d) to provide a communication platform to all relevant stakeholders: policy makers, academia, industry and scientific management. The Workshop was addressed to companies with R&D or production capacities, having potential for collaborative innovation, and to scientific institutions involved in particle accelerator R&D.

The main conclusions were that European industry is ready to play a more important role in the development of particle accelerator technologies, going from a traditional position of supplier of services or products to the role of co-innovator in partnership with university and research institutions. This positive attitude was particularly sensitive at the level of SME's that are often run by a management with scientific background and expertise, supporting innovation in its quest of new markets and applications. Innovation ecosystems can be developed around RIs supported by efficient mechanisms to facilitate knowledge and technology transfer between public institutions and private companies.

Industry acknowledged that working with research centres offers unique opportunities for R&D and innovation but also challenges given the discontinuity in R&D projects. Designing long-term large-scale research infrastructures represent the best chance for setting a new frame of co-innovation.

Financing of co-innovation remains an issue, because European industry has little resources to invest in high-risk R&D programmes. Sharing of funding and risks with the public sector (national or EC research and innovation programmes) is considered essential.

5. I.FAST, a recent experience in structuring a large accelerator R&I initiative based on co-innovation

To prepare in 2019 the new Innovation Pilot proposal I.FAST (Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology), the accelerator community represented by ARIES and TIARA has set up a joint Working Group to define content and structure of the new project. The goal of this initiative was to profit of the new project to define and test a new way of structuring projects within the accelerator community.

The Working Group has initially analysed different configurations for collaborative R&I initiatives, identifying two models as the most relevant for particle accelerator research, corresponding to most of the demands from the community:

- Development of fundamental technologies at low Technology Readiness Level (TRL), ranging between 2 (technology formulator) and 4 (small scale prototype).
- Construction of prototypes or demonstrators of higher performance technologies or instrumentations - including testing, at higher TRL, ranging between 4 (small scale prototype) and 7 (demonstration system).

For both categories, co-funding at the level of 50% from industrial partners was considered as an appropriate trade-off between the requirement of companies to share the cost and risk of R&D activities, and the requirement from research institutions of a correct involvement level from the company. The co-funding allows as well selecting between competing companies based among other factors on the level of the proposed co-funding. While R&D activities in the second category (called “Prototypes”) should have a longer duration (4 years or more), activities in the first category (“Developments”) can be shorter (2 years), but a continuation should be possible in case of success.

These considerations were applied in the preparation of the I.FAST proposal (Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology) to the H2020 call INFRAINNOV-04-2020 (Innovation pilots) that took place in 2019/20. A call for proposals under these guidelines was organised in summer 2019, with an excellent response from the accelerator and industry community. A total of 101 proposals were received, 86 of them involving industry at different levels (51 for Developments, 35 for Prototypes).

The criteria for the selection of projects were defined by the TIARA Collaboration Council, after consulting the different accelerator user communities and the industry representatives in ARIES. They are listed below:

- Scientific and technological excellence

- Impact on Research Infrastructures, their users and/or society
- Methodology
- Innovation content
- Transnationality and integration
- Co-funding rate
- Risk management
- Cost vs. Impact
- Extent and quality of industry involvement
- Efficient use of resources and environmental impact
- Coherence with and impact on priorities of the European accelerator community
- Continuity with previous programmes (ARIES, AMICI, etc.)

An Evaluation Committee composed of 13 members, out of which 5 were from industry, was appointed by TIARA to analyse the proposals received based on the above Criteria. The Committee members were provided with an Evaluation Guide specifying clear reference parameters for the points corresponding to each criterion. The process resulted in a ranking of proposals that was communicated on a public web site (<https://aries.web.cern.ch/outcome-evaluation>). The highest-ranking proposals entered into the accelerator community proposal I.FAST.

6. Towards a sustainable ecosystem for accelerator research and innovation in Europe

The experience gained in ARIES and in the preparation of the I.FAST proposal and the discussions with industrial partners in ARIES and with the accelerator community in TIARA, resulted in the definition of a stepwise approach to creating a sustainable ecosystem for particle accelerator research and innovation in Europe. The main steps in this roadmap, presented one by one in this chapter, are:

1. Creation of a permanent coordination and information body with European accelerator **industry**.
2. Enhanced coordination of accelerator R&I with the strategies of particle accelerator **user communities**.
3. Strengthening and enlargement of **TIARA**.
4. Definition of a long-term European **mission** for support to accelerator R&I, based on co-funding schemes.
5. **Facilitation, prioritization, and coordination** of R&I initiatives by an enlarged a strengthened TIARA.

6.1 STRENGTHENED AND COORDINATED INTERACTION WITH EUROPEAN ACCELERATOR INDUSTRY

Companies working with and for the particle accelerator community have declared their strong interest in co-innovation activities, and the wish to be informed on new initiatives and available EC instruments, and on new accelerator projects in preparation.

In parallel, in some European countries coordination bodies for science-related industry have been recently formed. INEUSTAR in Spain (Asociación Española de la Industria de la Ciencia) and PIGES in France (Association d'Industriels Français de Grands Equipements Scientifiques) both group national companies active in the development and construction of components for particle accelerators and other large scientific instruments. While it might be too early to imagine a similar structure at European level, a European committee representing industries active in the accelerator field could be easily constituted with representatives nominated by the national industry associations. A similar structure is already followed by the 12-member Industry Advisory Board of I.FAST, which at the end of the project in 2025 could continue as a permanent body representing industry in interactions with the particle accelerator community. Alternatively, this European-wide Committee could be established including all or part of the Industry Liaison Officers representing national industry in large accelerator laboratories like CERN.

The role of this permanent Accelerator-Industry Committee would be to interact with TIARA and with other accelerator user committees, to:

- identify opportunities and funding schemes for co-innovation programmes with the accelerator community,
- collect information on long-term R&D strategies of the accelerator community,
- provide industry opinion on commercial markets to be addressed by new or existing accelerator applications for society, for example in medicine, energy, environment, and security.

6.2 COORDINATION OF ACCELERATOR R&I WITH THE STRATEGIES OF USER COMMUNITIES

Traditionally, the most stringent demands on particle accelerators come from particle physics that drives the most advanced accelerator developments thanks to its cutting-edge requirements and to the strong commitment of all the community involved in this research. While it is essential that a coordination body for R&I on accelerators keeps a close and direct connection with the strategy groups expressed by this community, other communities must contribute to a shared roadmap for accelerator R&I, introducing their specific requirements and identifying exploitable synergies. This concerns in particular accelerators for nuclear physics, for synchrotron light sources, for neutron science, and for energy applications. A common widely supported R&I plan for accelerators must also incorporate the additional growing demands from the expanding field of societal applications of accelerators, first of all from the extremely challenging medical field, but as well from applications in old and new domains of environment, security, industrial production, food safety, etc.

To exploit synergies between the communities of particle accelerator users, an accelerator R&D collaboration like TIARA will have to establish and maintain connections with the strategy groups of the different communities and with their main projects. A list of different communities making use of particle accelerators, of their respective accelerator challenges, and of their main European sites and coordination bodies is given in the following Table.

Community	Accelerator goals	Main RI's	Strategy Groups
Particle Physics	High Energy, High Luminosity	CERN	ECFA, European Strategy, CERN Council, LDG
Nuclear Physics	High intensity, low-medium energy	GANIL, INFN labs, GSI/FAIR	NuPECC
Photon science	High brilliance	DESY, ESRF, MAX-IV, Diamond, Elettra, ...	LEAPS
Neutron science	High neutron flux	ESS, ISIS	LENS
Energy	High intensity, high energy	IFMIF, MYRRHA	
Medical applications	High patient throughput, low cost and size	HIT, MIT, CNAO, MedAustron	
Industry applications	High intensity, portability		
Environment and Food	High flux		IIA

ECFA: European Committee for Future Accelerators, is advisory to the CERN management and Council on the future of physics with high-energy accelerators (<https://ecfa.web.cern.ch/>).

LDG: Laboratory' Directors Group, established by the CERN Council with the aim to facilitate the implementation of the European Strategy for Particle Physics.

NuPECC: The Nuclear Physics European Collaboration Committee, an Expert Committee of the European Science Foundation to develop the strategy for European Collaboration in nuclear science (<http://www.nupecc.org/>)

LEAPS: League of European Accelerator-based Photon Sources, a consortium initiated by the Directors of the Synchrotron Radiation and Free Electron Laser user facilities in Europe to promote the quality and impact of research carried out at each facility (<https://leaps-initiative.eu/>).

LENS: League of advanced European Neutron Sources, a consortium to promote cooperation between European-level neutron infrastructure providers (<https://www.lens-initiative.org/>).

IIA: International Irradiation Association, an organisation to support the global irradiation industry and its scientific community (<https://iiaglobal.com/>).

Table 1: Accelerator user communities and their challenges, projects, and strategy groups

6.3 STRENGTHENING AND ENLARGEMENT OF TIARA

TIARA has so far played a key role in coordinating submission of proposals from the particle accelerator community to the different EC Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation. In future, this role must be continued and strengthened in the directions of representing the entire accelerator community towards the European Commission, of playing a direct role in the selection of R&D activities to be part of projects submitted to the EC calls, and finally in directly managing large initiatives for support of accelerator R&I coming from the EC or from other entities.

The mission of the reinforced TIARA would be:

- collecting input on strategic directions for particle accelerator R&D from the accelerator user communities and from the European Commission,
- maintaining a database of the European institutions active in accelerator R&D and of their competences, based on the existing list of partners in the past EC-supported projects, and including a database of European industry connected with accelerators,
- identifying synergies and collaboration opportunities within the enlarged particle accelerator community, involving national and international research centres, universities, and industry,
- connecting with similar initiatives and accelerator R&D programmes outside of Europe,
- selecting and prioritising R&D initiatives from the accelerator community, to be included in collaborative R&D projects supported by the European Commission or by other sources,
- identifying and facilitating co-funding schemes for financing accelerator R&D programme, including funding from European Commission, national and international research institutions, industry, and private donors and sponsors.
- managing funding schemes intended to support particle accelerator R&I,
- identifying the needs from the community and defining common strategies and initiatives for education and training in particle accelerators,
- providing outreach on accelerator challenges that are addressed at a coordinated European level, on the achievements, including societal challenges and accelerator applications,
- highlighting both needs and redundancies in European accelerator technological infrastructure, required for research and construction of new accelerators, and fostering its coordinated development.

This renewed mission should be defined in a new Memorandum of Understanding defining the role and scope of TIARA, or alternatively in a wider Collaboration Agreement among the present TIARA members, possibly extended to new partners and to consortia of smaller entities – as is the case already now with the Polish, Nordic, and Baltic consortia of universities and research centres participating in TIARA. Funding for the functioning of TIARA should come, as is the case already now, from in-kind or cash contributions of the members.

6.4 INTRODUCTION OF LONG-TERM EUROPEAN PROGRAMMES FOR SUPPORT TO ACCELERATOR R&I

The present report underlines the tremendous impact of particle accelerator R&I research and innovation on European science and society but at the same time indicates that this branch of science and technology requires large investments and long development times, which must be supported by adequate long-term strategies and funding.

Although internal strategic planning for accelerator R&I is already carried out by individual communities as e.g. the particle physics community, and collaborative projects for accelerator R&D are constantly being set up between individual laboratories, we believe that the establishment of a wider, better sustainable, and more effective European ecosystem for accelerator research and innovation might result in better and more cost effective scientific output, larger synergies between scientific fields, and an improved transfer of accelerator technologies to industry and eventually to the whole society. A Europe-wide accelerator ecosystem cannot be funded by national programmes only but requires a strong commitment from the European Commission, at the level of similar initiatives being initiated in the US.

The intervention of the Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation of the European Commission is essential because:

- it provides a well-defined frame to structure large collaborations, with clear objectives and deliverables.
- it motivates scientific communities to collaborate on common objectives, achieving synergies and cross-fertilisation.
- it allows coordinating the agenda of the scientific communities with EC priorities, like societal missions or widening of the Research Area.
- it provides a “seed” funding for research activities that will generate equivalent levels of co-funding from national or internal funding sources and from industry, and possibly leverage additional funding from other sources .

We consider that future programmes to support particle accelerator research and innovation within the EC Framework Programmes should take the form of a **multi-year mission with adequate funding, at the level of some 10 M€/year**.

This funding level corresponds to less than a factor of 2 increase with respect to the average overall amount of funding to the accelerator community over the last 20 years (Fig. 1) and is still considerably lower than the present DOE effort in the US to support particle accelerator, of the order of 15 M\$ (see Section 3). The time span of this mission should cover a full Framework Programme or at least a large fraction of it, to allow adequate long-term planning.

The strategic input to this “accelerator mission” should come from the European Commission, to be then translated into well-defined goals by a committee like a strengthened TIARA, possibly integrating representatives from the EC and from European industry.

Within this mission, different types of calls could be issued, their number and objectives to be defined by the EC and by other scientific planning structures like ESFRI. The calls should range from large scale more generic innovation initiatives in the line of the present Innovation Pilot I.FAST, to project intended to define innovative concepts for new accelerator-based Research Infrastructures, to specific calls following the priorities of the Commission on mission areas or widening actions. Long-term (5-10 years) should be accompanied by structured revisions, giving the possibility of redirecting investments following changes or priorities or accordingly to the success of previous developments.

All these initiatives should be based on co-funding schemes, following a well-established model in the accelerator community. The level of the EC contribution could easily be close to the 50% level (EC contribution over total project cost) applied for recent initiatives like ARIES and I.FAST. Such a co-funding structure would allow, for a total EC contribution of 10 M€/year, to coordinate and focus on common objectives a total effort of about 20 M€/year. As was the case in ARIES, it is expected that the recognition of being selected for a cutting-edge accelerator R&I project might attract additional funding by national agencies, further increasing the leverage factor of the initial EC contribution.

The initiatives within the accelerator mission should devote an adequate funding to societal applications of accelerators and to their outreach to the European public, with the goal of addressing global challenges, and of underlining the impact of basic research on society.

Co-innovation with industry at different TRL levels should be another important feature of this scheme, following in the successful line of I.FAST. In the case of I.FAST about 25% of the EC contribution goes to industry, and similar fractions of support to innovative European companies can be considered for future programmes.

6.5 FACILITATION AND PRIORITIZATION OF R&I INITIATIVES BY AN ENLARGED AND STRENGTHENED TIARA

While the objectives of the calls have to be agreed with the Commission, their content in terms of scientific goals and structure of the Consortium can be managed internally by the accelerator community, via TIARA in its present or in an enlarged form, as was successfully done for the I.FAST project (Section 5).

A scheme of the resulting “ecosystem” for European accelerator research and innovation is presented in Figure 5.

A sustainable ecosystem for European particle accelerator research and innovation

Figure 5: structure of the ecosystem for accelerator research and innovation

7. References

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8. Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ARIES	Accelerator Research and Innovation for European Science and Society
CLIC	Compact Linear Collider
DOE	Department of Energy
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures
ESGARD	European Strategy Group on Accelerator Research and Development
IFAST	Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology
TIARA	Test Infrastructure and Accelerator Research Area
TRL	Technology Readiness Level